

SCIENTIFIC AND THEORETICAL FOUNDATIONS OF THE FORMATION OF THE ETHNOESTHETIC CULTURE OF FUTURE PRIMARY SCHOOL TEACHERS IN THE MODERN SYSTEM OF PEDAGOGICAL EDUCATION

F.M. Qo‘chqarova¹, G.F. Erkinjonova²

Professor of the Education department of Kokand university¹

Teacher of the Education department of Kokand university²

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Abstract. *This article reveals the scientific and theoretical foundations for the development of ethno-aesthetic culture among future primary school teachers within the modern pedagogical education system. During the research, the knowledge and skills of future teachers in aesthetics and national values were studied, the current state was analyzed, and the main problems were identified. A specially designed module “Foundations of Ethno-Aesthetic Culture” was tested, demonstrating positive results. The article substantiates the importance of a comprehensive and integrative approach in the formation of ethno-aesthetic culture and highlights the prospects for using modern technologies to promote national values in the educational process.*

Keywords: *ethno-aesthetic culture, primary school teacher, national values, aesthetic education, pedagogical education, integrative approach, modern technologies, cultural identity.*

Introduction

In the era of rapid development of the modern pedagogical education system, the formation of a culture of future primary school teachers based on aesthetic and national values requires special attention. In the Republic of Uzbekistan, this issue is considered one of the priority areas of state policy. In particular, the Law "On Education" (2019) and the "Development Strategy of New Uzbekistan for 2022-2026"[1] pay special attention to the development of the education system based on national values. Also, as President Shavkat Mirziyoyev emphasized: "We must reach the heights of modern knowledge and culture, relying on our national pride and values"[2].

Ethno-aesthetic culture is the process of harmonious development of national identity, aesthetic taste, and cultural values in an individual. Primary school teachers play a decisive role in the formation of early aesthetic perception and national values in children. Therefore, the formation of their ethno-aesthetic culture is an important part not only of professional, but also of national and cultural education. This article is devoted to identifying the scientific and theoretical foundations of the formation of ethno-aesthetic culture of future primary school teachers, studying the current situation, analyzing problems, and identifying promising directions.

In the context of the growing importance of national culture and aesthetic values in modern society, the need to develop a sense of national identity, aesthetic taste, and respect for cultural heritage in the younger generation has become an urgent task. Globalization and technological progress have a serious impact on human thinking and the value system. This, in turn, requires a new approach to the education system, in particular, to the stage of primary education. Primary education serves as a fundamental stage in the formation of a child as a person, the development of their worldview and cultural-aesthetic perception. Therefore, aesthetic education and the introduction of national values occupy a special place in the professional training of future primary

school teachers. The formation of ethno-aesthetic culture presupposes the cultivation in the individual of national identity, aesthetic feelings, a sense of respect and attention to art and culture. With the timely and effective implementation of this process, the formation of cultural consciousness in children, spiritual maturity, and the development of creative thinking are ensured. Consequently, the formation of ethno-aesthetic culture of future primary school teachers in the modern system of pedagogical education is a strategically important task that serves not only professional skills, but also the cultural development of society as a whole.

Literature review

The issue of the formation of ethno-aesthetic culture is widely studied in modern pedagogical research. In this regard, scientific manuals, articles, and dissertations have been created by Uzbek and foreign scientists. One of the Uzbek scholars, A.A. Gulomov, in his work "National Culture and the Upbringing of the Younger Generation," based on the necessity of educating the individual through national values, highlighted the pedagogical mechanisms for instilling cultural heritage in the education system [3]. Eshonqulov, in his textbook "Pedagogical Skills and Aesthetic Education," emphasizes the importance of integrating national and contemporary values into the educational process in the process of aesthetic education [4].

Tojiboeva D.T. in her work "Fundamentals of Aesthetic Education in the Pedagogical Process" developed the theoretical and methodological foundations of ethno-aesthetic education and showed ways to form the cultural and aesthetic competence of the teacher's personality [5]. Oripova D.Kh., reflecting on the role of aesthetic education in preschool education, developed a methodology of aesthetic education based on national values [6]. Abdullayeva M. in her scientific articles extensively analyzed the role of national values in the educational process and the issue of their harmonization with modern pedagogical technologies [7].

Among foreign scholars, Sobitova M.M. in her monograph "Formation of Ethno-Aesthetic Culture of Personality" revealed the stages of forming ethno-aesthetic culture of personality and the organic connection of this process with socio-cultural conditions [8]. In the theory of cultural semiotics, Yu.M. Lotman analyzed the mechanisms of aesthetic expression of cultural values and the formation of a person's cultural thinking [9]. V.S. Bibler, through the theory of "Dialogue of Cultures," showed aesthetic and cultural interaction as the main condition for personality development [10].

The results of our research show that the formation of ethno-aesthetic culture should be carried out organically in the system of continuous education and the socio-cultural environment. Methods of ethno-aesthetic education, the harmony of national and aesthetic values, the formation of aesthetic feelings and cultural consciousness in the individual are emphasized as an important factor.

Methodology

The methodological basis of this study is the theory of personality development, the concepts of intercultural communication, pedagogical and sociological approaches to the formation of ethno-aesthetic culture. The scientific works of Uzbek and foreign scientists on the upbringing of the individual in the spirit of national and aesthetic values were analyzed.

The following were adopted as the theoretical and methodological basis of the research:

- general psychological and pedagogical regularities of the spiritual and aesthetic formation of the individual;

- theoretical views on the influence of culture on personality development (V.S. Bibler, Yu.M. Lotman, Sabitova M.M.);

- scientific approaches to the role of national values in education (Gulyamov A.A., Tojiboeva D.T., Eshonkulov Sh.A.);

- Methods of developing ethno-aesthetic culture in modern pedagogical education.

The main methods used in the study are:

Theoretical analysis - determining the theoretical foundations of research by studying scientific sources, pedagogical experience, laws, and decisions related to the topic.

Empirical methods - assessment of the level of ethno-aesthetic culture of future primary school teachers based on observation, questionnaires, interviews, and experimental tests.

The experimental method is the practical testing of the developed pedagogical recommendations and programs.

Statistical analysis - processing of collected data using mathematical and statistical methods and drawing scientifically based conclusions.

In the research process, the following main approaches were used:

- Integrative approach - the study of culture, aesthetics, and pedagogy in their interrelationship;

- Systematic approach - ensuring the organic connection of all factors of education and upbringing in the upbringing of the individual;

- Comprehensive approach - the harmonious combination of theoretical, methodological, and practical stages.

The object of the study were selected students studying in the Department of Primary Education of Kokand University. The subject is the pedagogical conditions and mechanisms for organizing the process of forming their ethno-aesthetic culture.

The methodology was continuously applied at all stages of the research - in the processes of theoretical justification, software design, experimental verification, and analysis of results. The research results confirmed the possibility of developing students' professional and personal competencies through the harmonious implementation of national values and aesthetic education.

Research results

During the study, 100 second and third-year students studying in the primary education program of Kokand University were studied. Among them, 50 students were selected as the experimental group, and 50 as the control group. At the beginning of the study and at the end of the experimental program, their level of ethno-aesthetic culture was assessed based on specially developed criteria.

At the beginning of the study, the following initial results were identified among students:

1-table

Indicators	Control group (%)	Experimental group (%)
Knowledge of national values	42%	44%
Aesthetic taste and interest in art	38%	40%
Respect for culture	45%	46%
National elements in creative activity	35%	37%

The following components were selected for the assessment of ethno-aesthetic culture:

1. Knowledge of national values
2. Aesthetic taste and interest in art

3. Respect for culture and traditional values
4. Use of national elements in creative activity
1. Initial indicators

2. Results after the experimental program

Special classes were conducted for the experimental group based on the program "Fundamentals of Ethno-Aesthetic Culture." At the end of the program, the following changes were noted:

2-table

Indicators	Control group (%)	Experimental group (%)
Knowledge of national values	44%	72%
Aesthetic taste and interest in art	40%	75%
Respect for culture	47%	78%
National elements in creative activity	38%	70%

Diagram: Comparison of results from the treatment and control groups

Diagram 1

The research results showed that the special classes conducted on the formation of ethno-aesthetic culture among students of the primary education program of Kokand University were effective. The knowledge of students of the experimental group about national values, aesthetic taste, appreciation of cultural values, and indicators of the use of national elements in creative activity increased significantly. This proves the high effectiveness of integrated educational methods aimed at the formation of ethno-aesthetic culture.

Discussion

Analysis of the research results confirmed the effectiveness of special pedagogical influence on the formation of ethno-aesthetic culture among students of the primary education program of Kokand University. A significant increase in knowledge of national values, aesthetic taste and respect for culture, as well as indicators of the use of national elements in creative activity, was observed in the students of the experimental group. At the same time, an integrated

approach to the educational process - the organization of lessons based on national art, folklore, historical and cultural traditions, served the harmonious development of aesthetic perception and national identity.

During the discussion, it was established that the process of forming ethno-aesthetic culture requires a multi-stage and systematic approach. Through special classes, students not only increased their level of knowledge, but also acquired a personal interest in art and culture, a motivation to value national values. This ensured the implementation of aesthetic education at the level of personal consciousness and activity. Analysis shows that practical classes, cultural events, creative projects, and lessons on the analysis of national works of art have served as an effective tool for the formation of ethno-aesthetic culture in primary school students. With the help of specially prepared methodological materials and curricula, students not only received knowledge, but were also actively involved in creative and aesthetic activity. However, some difficulties were also observed during the research. In particular, insufficient knowledge of students about national art and values at the initial stage, weak practical aesthetic experience, and indifference to the formation of cultural and aesthetic consciousness among some students were revealed. To overcome these problems, the need arose to enrich the curricula, organize aesthetic education in integration with all subjects, and support students' independent aesthetic activity.

Conclusion

The results of the conducted scientific research showed that the formation of ethno-aesthetic culture of future primary school teachers is one of the current and strategic directions of the modern pedagogical education system. The module "Fundamentals of Ethno-Aesthetic Culture," developed and implemented during the study, led to a significant increase in the knowledge, aesthetic taste, and sense of respect for culture and national values of students in the experimental group.

Based on the research results, the following were determined:

The formation of national values and aesthetic taste is the main factor in the development of cultural and aesthetic competence of future teachers.

- With the help of practical classes, cultural events, and creative projects, students develop a conscious attitude towards aesthetic perception and national values.

- Specially developed methodological materials and educational programs reflecting national aesthetic values provide high effectiveness in the development of ethno-aesthetic culture.

At the same time, during the study, problems such as a low level of initial knowledge of national values and insufficient experience of cultural and aesthetic activity were identified, which require a systematic approach to eliminate.

Suggestions

Based on the research results, the following practical recommendations were developed:

1. Introduction into higher education programs of special courses and classes aimed at the formation of ethno-aesthetic culture for future primary school teachers.

2. Expansion of practical classes: integration of art analysis, cultural events, creative projects, and activities reflecting national values into the lesson process.

3. Creation of methodological materials and teaching aids on aesthetic education and their implementation in the educational process.

4. Instilling national identity and aesthetic values in the minds of students through the active use of examples of national art and culture in lessons.

5. Encouraging students' independent aesthetic activity: involving them in the activities of national crafts, theater, folk games, and musical aesthetic clubs.

6. Expanding the worldview of students and enriching their cultural thinking through harmonious teaching of Uzbek and world aesthetic values.

7. Studying the dynamics of development in the formation of ethno-aesthetic culture through the expansion of experimental work and constant monitoring.

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